

Research Support to Researchers in Digital Era

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Citation of Article: Jadhav, V. S., & Shelke, S. M. (2025). Research Support to Researchers in Digital Era. International Journal of Classified Research Techniques & Advances (IJCRTA) ISSN: 2583- 1801, 5 (2), pg. 48-52. ijcrta.org

DOI: [10.5281/zenodo.17219166](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17219166)

ABSTRACT:

This article describes the roles of librarians in a research library, particularly in the digital era. Librarians' roles vary from the custodian of resources to providers of a diverse nature of activities ranging from collection development, organization of knowledge, information services, preservation and conservation, and management. The traditional ways of performing these functions is being eroded by modern technology. This calls for changes in the products and services of research libraries to the research community served. These changes and the roles that librarians play are discussed in this article.

1. INTRODUCTION:

The library environment at the beginning of the twenty-first century is unimaginably different to that of a century ago. The advent of computers and automation irrevocably changed the practice of librarianship. Patrons today are encouraged to be independent researchers, with open access collections and self-access services at their disposal. Some administrators view the emerging electronic environment as an opportunity to cut costs. Librarians could be excused for wondering if there is a role for them in the virtual library environment. As a result libraries are scoping, developing and implementing new roles and service models, especially in the relatively new area of research data.

2. RESEARCH:

Systematic observation of phenomena for the purpose of learning new facts or testing the application of theories to known facts called as research.

3. RESEARCHERS:

One who conducts research in the field of scientific research, also called an investigator or scientist.

4. NEED OF RESEARCH:

- Extension of knowledge
- Bring to light information that might never be discovered during the ordinary course of life

- Establish generalizations and general laws which contributes to theory building
- Verify and test the existing facts and theories
- Initiate, formulate, deflect, and Need and Purpose
- Analyze interrelationships between variables and to derive causal explanations
- Find solutions to problems
- Develop new tools, concepts and theories
- Aid in planning and contributes to national development
- Disseminate research findings to create awareness of current situations and problems Need and Purpose.
- Formulate strategies and policies
- Brings prestige to the person and the institution
- Promote progress of the society

5. ROLE OF LIBRARIES OR KRC TO RESEARCHERS:

Librarians Support research, teaching, and learning through their advanced expertise in a wide range of subject areas, interdisciplinary research and teaching to encourage the researchers, **Data Management Services** assists researchers for research data to enhance its preservation and access now and into the future.

General references get research help in person, or through email, phone, or instant chat. Tips for using bibliographic citation management tools.

Data and statistical software support for finding and using social science data for quantitative and qualitative analysis.

Digitization services provides digital scanning, reformatting and capture of born digital materials.

Multimedia and technology use hardware, software, training, and consulting for students, faculty, and instructors using multimedia in their work.

Special and archival collection references finding and using manuscripts, rare books, archival materials, and other Special Collections resources.

Digital repositories offers services for preserving and managing access to research content of long-term value, archived faculty, students, and departments and also preserves extensive digital library collections.

6. LIBRARY SUPPORT TO RESEARCHERS:

6.1. SUPPORT FOR UNDERTAKING RESEARCH:

6.1.1 LITERATURE SEARCHING:

Library staff can provide support for literature searching, including: guidance on which resources are appropriate for your topic, support for carrying out an initial literature search, guidance on carrying out cited reference searching, Support for developing advanced search strategies to ensure comprehensive literature retrieval, including searching for systematic reviews.

6.1.2 SCOPING A RESEARCH PROJECT:

When you first embark on a research project, specialist library staff can help you to scope your project to determine the current level of knowledge existing in that field, including support for: carrying out searches for literature, identifying relevant conference abstracts and proceedings, identifying similar research in progress and research groups with similar interests in the UK and beyond.

6.1.3 KEEPING UP TO DATE WITH RESEARCH:

Library staff can provide guidance on the many tools available to keep you up to date with research in your field or issues and events that may influence your research.

- Journal article alerts
- Subject search alerts
- Cited reference
- Social media
- Social networking Social citation sharing
- Other alerts
- General web alerting services
- Conferences and events

6.1.4 REFERENCE MANAGEMENT & CITATION:

Library staff can advise on systematic approaches to managing bibliographic references as well as standards for citing references.

Reference management software enables you to create your own database of references relevant to your research and then to insert references and format them automatically in the citation style of your choice within a Word document.

Library staff can advise on correctly citing your sources and you can find further information on **References, Citations and Avoiding Plagiarism** web pages.

6.1.5 COPYRIGHT & IPR ADVICE:

Library staff offer advice on legislation surrounding **copyright** and licensing schemes, issues relating to the work you create including **Intellectual Property Rights**, Creative Commons and model licenses to publish, and the **re-use of copyright material** in your own work.

6.1.6 USE OF SOFTWARE:

Support for the use of other software is provided provide training on software, learning technologies and administration systems, including essential computer skills and statistical software.

6.2 ACCESS TO RESOURCES:

6.2.1 ACCESSING CATALOGUES & E-RESOURCES:

Library Services' one-stop access point to finding printed and electronic resources. For detailed information on searching Library Services provides access to a wide range of electronic resources, including an extensive collection of databases and e-journals.

6.2.2 SPECIAL COLLECTIONS:

Special Collections offers considerable holdings of archives, rare books and manuscripts which support research and teaching.

6.2.3 STORES, INTERLENDING & DOCUMENT SUPPLY:

Some printed materials are held at the Library is not available at another library locally, it may be possible to obtain it through the Interlending & Document Supply Service.

6.2.4 ACCESSING OTHERS LIBRARIES & ARCHIVES:

As a member Library, you are entitled to use many other libraries, Access scheme that allows academic staff and research postgraduates from participating institutions to borrow material from other member libraries.

6.2.5 SUGGESTION FROM NEW MATERIALS:

If you would like to suggest a book or other item for purchase by the Library, please complete library form to the appropriate site or subject librarian for consideration.

6.2.6 SUBJECT SPECIALISTS & GUIDES:

Library Services has a team of site and subject librarians who can offer specialist research support and advice. For introductory information about the collections and resources available in your subject area, see the list of subject guides.

6.2.7 THESES:

For information about theses, including which theses we hold and how you can obtain copies of research theses

6.3 DISSEMINATION, EVALUATION & PRESERVATION OF RESEARCH:

6.3.1 BIBLIOMETRICS:

Bibliometrics webpage are a guide to ways to approach bibliometric measures and how to interpret and use the findings, bibliometric policy and the wider context, types of metrics, issues surrounding the use of metrics and support and training available in bibliometrics.

Library staffs provide training and support on using the resources available to identify citation metrics such as average times cited, h-index and journal impact factors. These resources comprise web of science (including Web of Science Core Collection, Journal Citation Reports, Essential Science Indicators, Biosis, InCites) and Scopus.

6.3.2 PUBLICATION DATA COLLECTION:

Library staff can assist with the collection of research publication data for publication returns, grant applications and quality assessment

6.3.3 OPEN ACCESS:

Open access maximises the impact of your research, and leads to increased citations.

6.3.4 DATA MANAGEMENT:

Research Data Management Webpages offers information, how-to guides and support to plan ahead for data management.

6.3.5 ELECTRONIC THESES:

Electronic theses offer guidance on the preparation and deposit of electronic copies of research theses.

REFERENCE:

<http://library.stanford.edu/research-services>

<http://www.freewebs.com/sampathkumar/u31.pdf>

<http://www.ucl.ac.uk/library/research-support>

<http://www.webster-dictionary.org/definition/Research>

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IJCRTA